

AN ATTEMPT TOWARDS THE SYNTHESIS OF β -SELINENE*

BY D. K. BANERJEE AND P. S. HALWE

An attempt to obtain β -selinene (I) by the pyrolysis of 4-acetoxymethyl-6-(α -acetoxymethylethyl)-9-methyldecalin (IV) has been described. A synthesis of (IV) has been reported, and proof of the structure of the important intermediate, methyl 6-methyl-6-ethoxycarbonylcyclohexanone-3- α -propionate, has been provided.

The sesquiterpene hydrocarbon, selinene, was first isolated by Ciamician and Silber (*Ber.*, 1897, 30, 496) from the fruit of *Apium graveolens*, and was assigned the structure (I) (Simonsen, 'The Terpenes', Vol. III, Cambridge University Press, p. 32, 1952). The relationship of eudesmol to selinene was established by Ruzicka *et al.* (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1931, 14, 1178) and eudesmol was assigned the absolute configuration (II) by correlating it to the steroids of known absolute configuration (Woodward *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 313).

The present investigation was undertaken with a view to synthesising β -selinene. It appeared to us that the diol (III) through pyrolysis of its acetate (IV) (Bailey *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1953, 75, 4780; 1954, 76, 2251; 1955, 77, 75) might yield a bicyclic system with the characteristic features of β -selinene (I).

The scheme for the synthesis of the diol (III) has been outlined below.

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We first attempted to prepare ethyl *cyclohexanone-3-methylmalonate* (V) by methylation of ethyl *cyclohexanone-3-malonate* using sodium methoxide, but only a very poor yield of the methylated product could be obtained due to retrogression of the Michael reaction. Condensation of Δ^2 -*cyclohexenone* with diethyl methylmalonate (2 moles) in presence of sodium methoxide (1 mole) in methanol (Masanao Matasui *et al.*, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1954, 27, 7) afforded only 25% yield of the adduct (V), while condensation in presence of 1/6 mole of sodium ethoxide in ether (Michael and Ross, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 4598) furnished ethyl *cyclohexanone-3-methylmalonate* (V) in 74% yield. During the aforementioned Michael reaction a small quantity of an alkali-soluble product (ca. 1%), which exhibited violet colour with ethanolic ferric chloride, was also obtained, but not further investigated. Hydrolysis of the keto-malonic ester (V) with hydrochloric acid or sulphuric acid or methanolic alkali afforded only 25-36% yield of *cyclohexanone-3- α -propionic acid* (VIIIa). The keto group of (V) was next protected by preparing ethyl 1-cyano-2-methyl-2-dioxycyclohexane-3-methylmalonate (VIa). The latter was saponified by refluxing with an excess

of methanolic alkali followed by careful acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid to furnish the di-acid (VIb), which in the crude state was decarboxylated and esterified with diazomethane, followed by regeneration of the ketone (VIIIb) from its ketal (VIIb) to obtain methyl *cyclohexanone-3- α -propionate* (VIIIb) in 52% yield. Prior regeneration of the keto-acid (VIIIa) from (VIIa), followed by esterification, however, increased the yield to 68%. Methyl 6-ethoxycarbonyl*cyclohexanone-3- α -propionate* (IX) was obtained by condensing methyl *cyclohexanone-3- α -propionate* (VIIIb) with diethyl oxalate in an ethanolic solution of sodium ethoxide, followed by pyrolysis of the resulting glyoxalate, in 61% yield. Methylation of the aforementioned β -keto-ester (IX) using sodium dust and methyl iodide in benzene (Linstead and Millidge, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 478) furnished methyl 6-methyl-6-ethoxycarbonyl*cyclohexanone-3- α -propionate* (X) in 90% yield.

That the condensation of diethyl oxalate with methyl *cyclohexanone-3- α -propionate* (VIIIb) occurred in the C₆ position and not in the C₂ position was proved by conversion of methyl 6-methyl-6-ethoxycarbonyl*cyclohexanone-3- α -propionate* (X) into ethyl 6-methyl*cyclohexanone-3- α -propionate* (XIX) by treating the former with aqueous alkali, followed by esterification. The melting point of the semicarbazone of (XIX) remained undepressed on admixture with the semicarbazone of an authentic specimen of ethyl 6-methyl*cyclohexanone-3- α -propionate*. An authentic sample of (XIX) was prepared by a slight modification of the procedure of Mukherjee (this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 155) (vide Experimental).

Condensation of methyl 6-methyl-6-ethoxycarbonyl*cyclohexanone-3- α -propionate* (X) with ethyl cyanoacetate, using ammonium acetate and glacial acetic acid, was carried out by following essentially the conditions of Banerjee and Shafer (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 1931) to obtain ethyl 6-ethoxycarbonyl-6-methyl-3-(α -methoxycarbonylethyl)-*cyclohexylidene*cyanoacetate (XI) in 54% yield. The unsaturated cyano-ester (XI) was reduced with palladium charcoal as catalyst under pressure. The addition of acrylonitrile to the aforementioned cyano-ester (XII) was carried out in presence of 'Triton B' in dioxane to furnish ethyl 6-methyl-6-ethoxycarbonyl-3-(α -methoxycarbonylethyl)-*cyclohexyl*-(β -cyanoethyl)-cyanoacetate in 95% yield (XIII). The dicyano-ester (XIII) was hydrolysed and esterified to yield 6-methyl-6-ethoxycarbonyl-3-(α -ethoxycarbonylethyl)-1-(α -diethoxycarbonylpropyl)-*cyclohexane* (XIV) in 54% yield. Dieckmann cyclisation of the tetra-ester (XIV) afforded 1-keto-2,4-diethoxycarbonyl-6-(α -methoxycarbonylethyl)-9-methyldecalin, which was hydrolysed and decarboxylated by refluxing with dilute hydrochloric acid and subsequently esterified with diazomethane to yield 1-keto-4-methoxycarbonyl-6-(α -methoxycarbonylethyl)-9-methyldecalin (XV) (overall yield 58%). The decalone (XV) was reduced by Clemmensen's method and esterified with diazomethane to furnish 4-methoxycarbonyl-6-(α -methoxycarbonylethyl)-9-methyldecalin (XVI) in 70% yield. The di-ester (XVI) was next reduced with lithium aluminium hydride to afford 4-hydroxymethyl-6-(α -hydroxymethylethyl)-9-methyldecalin (III) in 90% yield. The diacetyl derivative (IV) was prepared by heating the diol (III) with acetic anhydride and pyridine in 85% yield. The pyrolysis of 4-acetoxymethyl-6-(α -acetoxymethylethyl)-9-methyldecalin (IV) according to the procedure

of Bailey (*loc. cit.*, 1953) provided a hydrocarbon in 29% yield, the analysis of which fits $C_{15}H_{24}$ (λ_{max}^{EtOH} 224 $m\mu$, $\log \epsilon$ 4.2). The hydrocarbon has the characteristic bands in I.R. region at 886 cm^{-1} ($\begin{matrix} R_1 \\ R_2 \end{matrix} > C=CH_2$) (Thompson and Whiffen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 1412) and 1625 cm^{-1}

(Naves, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1956, 292). The synthetic hydrocarbon appears to be a mixture of isomers of selinene.

EXPERIMENTAL *

Δ^2 -cycloHexenone was prepared from 2-chlorocyclohexanone ("Organic Syntheses", 1945, Vol. XXV, p. 22, John Wiley & Sons, New York) according to the procedure of Wanzlick (*Ber.*, 1955, 88, 69) in 59% yield.

Ethyl cycloHexanone-3-malonate was obtained according to the procedure of Bartlett and Woods (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 2933), b.p. $145-47^\circ/2$ mm, n_D^{25} 1.4613, yield 81%.

Ethyl cycloHexanone-3-methylmalonate (V).—To a solution of sodium (1.8 g., 1/6 mole) in anhydrous ethanol (4 c.c.) and dry ether (200 c.c.) diethyl methylmalonate (85 g.) ("Organic Syntheses", Vol. XVII, 1937, p. 54, John Wiley & Sons, New York) was added, followed by cyclohexenone (45 g.) in dry ether (100 c.c.), when a vigorous reaction ensued and the ether started refluxing. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 5 hours on a water bath. After cooling, acetic acid (5 c.c.) in water (50 c.c.) was added to it. The ethereal layer was first washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and then extracted with 2% ice-cold alkali, and finally washed with water. After removing the solvent the residue was distilled to provide unchanged cyclohexenone and diethyl methylmalonate (34 g.), b.p. up to $95^\circ/2$ mm, and ethyl cyclohexanone-3-methylmalonate, b.p. $158-60^\circ/1-2$ mm, n_D^{24} 1.4629; yield 93.55 g. (74%). (Found: C, 61.76; H, 8.34. $C_{14}H_{22}O_5$ requires C, 62.10; H, 8.15%).

The semicarbazone, after crystallisation from ethanol, melted at $149-50^\circ$. (Found: N, 12.81. $C_{15}H_{22}O_5N_3$ requires N, 12.84%).

The alkaline extract was acidified with cold HCl (dil.) and extracted with ether. After removing the solvent the residue was distilled, b.p. $52^\circ/2$ mm, yield 1 g. The distillate showed violet colour with alcoholic ferric chloride, but the product was not identified.

Ethyl 1-Ethylenedioxcyclohexane-3-methylmalonate (VIa).—A mixture of ethyl cyclohexanone-3-methylmalonate (154 g.), ethylene glycol (45 c.c.), *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (100 mg.), and benzene (300 c.c.) was refluxed in a flask fitted with a continuous water separator. The refluxing was continued till the water had ceased to separate (*ca.* 48 hours). The cooled reaction mixture was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water. After removing the solvent the product was distilled, b.p. $168-69^\circ/2$ mm, n_D^{26} 1.4672; yield 176 g. (98%). (Found: C, 60.70; H, 8.24. $C_{16}H_{26}O_6$ requires C, 61.15; H, 8.28%).

Methyl cycloHexanone-3- α -propionate (VIIIb).—(a). Ethyl 1-ethylenedioxcyclohexane-3-methylmalonate (60 g.) was refluxed for 4 hours with KOH (33 g.) in water (25 c.c.), and methanol

* All recorded m.p. and b.p.'s are uncorrected.

(325 c.c.). The methanol was distilled off and iced water was added to the product. The solution was made just acidic to litmus with ice-cold 6*N*-HCl and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water and dried over sodium sulphate. After removing the solvent the crude malonic acid derivative (VIb) was decarboxylated by heating with glass powder at 160° in an oil bath. After cooling, the acid (VIIa) was shaken with HCl (50 c.c., 10%) for 30 mins. with slight warming on the water bath (ca. 50-60°). The deketalised acid was taken in ether and the aqueous layer extracted with ether. The combined ether layer was washed with water. The crude *cyclohexanone-3- α -propionic acid* was esterified with diazomethane, prepared from 42 g. of nitrosomethylurea, in the usual way and purified by distillation, b.p. 109°/2 mm, n_D^{23} 1.4649; yield 25 g. (68%). (Found : C, 65.56; H, 8.61. $C_{10}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 65.22; H, 8.69%).

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 158-59°. (Found : N, 17.56. $C_{11}H_{19}O_3N_3$ requires N, 17.43%).

A small quantity of *cyclohexanone-3- α -propionic acid* was purified by short-path distillation, bath temperature 145-47°/1 mm, n_D^{25} 1.4838. (Found : C, 63.06; H, 8.37. $C_9H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 63.53; H, 8.23%).

(b). A mixture of ethyl *cyclohexanone-3-methylmalonate* (11 g.), KOH (7 g.) in water (6 c.c.), and methanol (50 c.c.) was refluxed for 2 hours on a water bath. The methanol was removed under diminished pressure and the product was diluted with water. The cooled reaction mixture was acidified with H_2SO_4 (dil.) and extracted several times with ether. The *cyclohexanone-3-methylmalonic acid*, obtained after removal of the solvent, was decarboxylated by heating with glass powder at 160° in a preheated oil bath to yield *cyclohexanone-3- α -propionic acid*, which was purified by short-path distillation, bath temperature 143-45°/2 mm, yield 1.7 g. (25%).

(c). A mixture of ethyl *cyclohexanone-3-methylmalonate* (12.36 g.), HCl (40 c.c.), and water (40 c.c.) was refluxed for 24 hours in an oil bath. After cooling, the keto-acid was extracted with ether, and after removing the solvent the residue was purified by short-path distillation, bath-temperature 140-42°/1-2 mm, yield 2.17 g. (28%).

Methyl 6-Ethoxycarbonylcyclohexanone-3- α -propionate (IX).—To sodium dust (3 g.) under dry ether (60 c.c.), cooled in a freezing mixture (ice and salt), was added dropwise dry ethanol (6 g.), and the mixture was left overnight. Ethyl oxalate (21 g.) was then added in the cold (0°). The reaction mixture on being kept aside for 3 hours was cooled in a freezing mixture (ice and salt) and methyl *cyclohexanone-3- α -propionate* (23.5 g.) was slowly added with continuous shaking. The reaction mixture was kept at 0° for 48 hours, when it turned deep red. It was diluted with iced water and the ether layer was extracted with 2% ice-cold alkali. The combined aqueous layer was acidified with ice-cold HCl (dil.) and extracted with ether; the ether extract was washed with water and dried over calcium chloride. After removing the solvent, the glyoxalate was heated with glass powder at 160-65° in a preheated oil bath till evolution of carbon monoxide had ceased; the product was distilled to furnish methyl 6-ethoxycarbonylcyclohexanone-3- α -propionate, b.p. 148-50°/1 mm, n_D^{23} 1.4762; yield 20 g. (61%). (Found : C, 61.08; H, 7.98. $C_{13}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 60.94; H, 7.81%).

Methyl 6-Methyl-6-ethoxycarbonylcyclohexanone-3- α -propionate (X).—The preceding ester (IX) (19.16 g.) was added dropwise to sodium dust (1.8 g.) in dry benzene (50 c.c.), cooled in ice and water, and allowed to stand overnight. Methyl iodide (20 c.c.) was added and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 hours. A further quantity of methyl iodide (10 c.c.) was added and the refluxing continued for 2 hours more. Water was added to the cooled reaction mixture and the benzene

layer washed with water. After removing the solvent the product was distilled, b.p. 155-57°/1-2 mm, n_D^{25} 1.4651; yield 18.34 g. (90%). (Found: C, 62.22; H, 8.73. $C_{14}H_{22}O_5$ requires C, 62.22; H, 8.15%). The product did not exhibit any colour with ethanolic ferric chloride.

Ethyl 6-Methylcyclohexanone-3- α -propionate (XIX).—A mixture of compound (X) (3.4 g.) and a solution of KOH (2.4 g.) in water (24 c.c.) was refluxed for 9 hours. The cooled solution was acidified with HCl (dil.) and extracted with ether-benzene. After removing the solvent mixture, the acid was dried in a desiccator. The crude dry keto-acid was refluxed with anhydrous ethanol (25 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (5 c.c.) for 20 hours. Brine was added to the cooled reaction mixture and extracted with ether-benzene mixture. The extract was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water. After removing the solvent the residue was distilled, b.p. 112°/1 mm, n_D^{25} 1.4588; yield 1.93 g. (85%). (Found: C, 67.99, H, 9.51. $C_{19}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 67.94; H, 9.43%).

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 169-70°. [(Reported m.p. 156° (Mukherjee, *loc. cit.*) and 169° (Gunstone and Tulloch, *J. Appl. Chem.*, 1954, 4, 291)]. (Found: N, 15.54. $C_{19}H_{23}O_3N_3$ requires N, 15.61%). This melting point was not depressed on admixture with an authentic sample.

An Authentic Specimen of the Semicarbazone of Ethyl 6-Methylcyclohexanone-3- α -propionate.—6-Ethoxycarbonyl-6-methyl- Δ^2 -cyclohexenone was prepared according to the procedure of Mukherjee (*loc. cit.*). The desired product had b.p. 113-16°/11 mm.

To a solution of sodium ethoxide, prepared from sodium (0.15 g.), dry ethanol (1 c.c.), and dry ether (50 c.c.), diethyl methylmalonate (5.5 g.) was added followed by 6-ethoxycarbonyl-6-methyl- Δ^2 -cyclohexenone (5.5 g.) in dry ether (25 c.c.). The mixture was refluxed for 6 hours. Acetic acid (1 c.c.) was added to the cooled reaction mixture, and the ether layer was separated and washed with water, 2% alkali, and again with water. After removing the solvent ethyl 6-methyl-6-ethoxycarbonylcyclohexanone-3-methylmalonate was distilled, b.p. 178-80°/1 mm, yield 7.5 g. (70%). The same compound was previously obtained by Mukherjee (*loc. cit.*) by methylation of ethyl 6-methyl-6-ethoxycarbonylcyclohexanone-3-malonate.

A mixture of ethyl 6-methyl-6-ethoxycarbonylcyclohexanone-3-methylmalonate (7.5 g.) and a solution of KOH (8 g.) in water (8 c.c.) was refluxed for 10 hours. The cooled reaction mixture after extraction with ether was acidified with cold HCl (dil.) and then extracted with ether-benzene mixture. The extract was washed with water and the solvent mixture removed. The residue was dried in a desiccator and then refluxed for 16 hours with dry ethanol (25 c.c.) and H_2SO_4 (2 c.c.). The ester was worked up in the usual way to obtain ethyl 6-methylcyclohexanone-3- α -propionate, b.p. 110°/1-2 mm, n_D^{27} 1.4588; yield 1.77 g. (45%).

The *semicarbazone* after crystallisation from ethanol melted at 169-70°.

Ethyl 6-Ethoxycarbonyl-6-methyl-3-(α -methoxycarbonylethyl)-cyclohexylidenecyanoacetate (XI).—A mixture of the ester (X) (37.5 g.), ethyl cyanoacetate (15.9 c.c.), ammonium acetate (6.9 g.), glacial acetic acid (10.5 c.c.), and benzene (38 c.c.) was refluxed in a flask fitted with a continuous water separator till the water had ceased to separate (*ca.* 25 hours). The reaction mixture was cooled and washed 6 times with water. After removing the solvent, the product was distilled to furnish (i) ethyl cyanoacetate, 4.6 g., b.p. 75°/1 mm; (ii) a mixture of (i) and (iii) (18.75 g.), b.p. 148-96°/1 mm; (iii) the pure unsaturated cyano-ester (XI), b.p. 200-205°/1 mm, n_D^{28} 1.4791; λ_{max}^{EtOH} 235 m μ , $\log \epsilon$ 3.94; yield 27.35 g. (54%). (Found: N, 3.83. $C_{18}H_{27}O_6N$ requires N, 3.83%).

Ethyl 6-Methyl-6-ethoxycarbonyl-3-(α -methoxycarbonylethyl)-cyclohexylcyanoacetate (XII).—Hydrogenation of the unsaturated cyano-ester (XI) (19 g.) was carried out at an initial pressure of 25 atoms. in the presence of palladised charcoal (5%, 0.3 g.) in purified ethanol (75 c.c.). The reduction was complete in 20 hours. Palladised charcoal was filtered off and the solvent removed. The residue was distilled, b.p. $170-72^{\circ}/1.6 \times 10^{-3}$ mm, $n_D^{22.5}$ 1.4741; yield 16.55 g. (89%). (Found: C, 61.93; H, 8.04; N, 3.66. $C_{19}H_{29}O_6N$ requires C, 61.98; H, 7.90; N, 3.81%).

6-Methyl-6-ethoxycarbonyl-3-(α -ethoxycarbonylethyl)-1-(α - γ -diethoxycarbonylpropyl)-cyclohexane (XIV).—To an ice-cold solution of the saturated cyano-ester (XII) (10.54 g.) and acrylonitrile (1.6 g.) in dioxane (10 c.c.) was slowly added "Triton B"; the mixture was kept in an ice bath for 1 hour with occasional swirling. The reaction mixture was kept for 7 days at the room temperature, when it turned deep brown. It was then taken up in benzene, washed thoroughly with HCl (dil.), and finally with water. The solvent was thoroughly removed leaving the crude product as a viscous oil, yield 11.5 g. (95%). This product could not be distilled without decomposition and it was not analysed.

The crude dicyano-ester (XIII) (11.51 g.) was refluxed for 60 hours with HCl (conc., 75 c.c.). The mixture was extracted with ether-benzene. The solvent mixture was removed and the crude tetracarboxylic acid (9.12 g.) after drying in *vacuo* was refluxed for 94 hours with a mixture of dry ethanol (100 c.c.) and H_2SO_4 (conc., 18 c.c.). The tetra-ester was worked up in the usual way, b.p. $195-200^{\circ}/1$ mm, yield 6.55 g. (54%). (Found: C, 62.99; H, 8.67. $C_{24}H_{40}O_8$ requires C, 63.13; H, 8.77%).

1-Keto-4-methoxycarbonyl-6-(α -methoxycarbonylethyl)-9-methyldecalin (XV).—To sodium dust (0.62 g.) under benzene (20 c.c.) was added the tetra-ester (XIV) (6.8 g.) through a separatory funnel in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The separatory funnel was then washed down with dry benzene (5 c.c.). The reaction started immediately and the mixture was refluxed for 9 hours. The product was cooled in an ice bath under nitrogen, and to it was added HCl (dil.). The benzene layer was separated and washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and water. The residue obtained after removal of the solvent gave a violet colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. A small portion of this β -keto-ester was purified by short-path distillation, bath temperature $145-50^{\circ}/1$ mm, for analysis. (Found: C, 64.86; H, 8.54. $C_{22}H_{37}O_7$ requires C, 64.39; H, 8.29%).

The aforementioned crude β -keto-ester was refluxed for 24 hours with 15% H_2SO_4 (dil., 50 c.c.). The cooled solution was extracted with ether-benzene. After removal of the solvent mixture the crude keto-acid (4.2 g.) was esterified with diazomethane, prepared from 4 g. of nitrosomethyl urea, to yield 1-keto-4-methoxycarbonyl-6-(α -methoxycarbonylethyl)-9-methyldecalin, b.p. $160-65^{\circ}/3.2 \times 10^{-2}$ mm, yield 2.56 g. (58%). (Found: C, 65.70; H, 8.31. $C_{17}H_{28}O_5$ requires C, 65.8; H, 8.38%).

4-Methoxycarbonyl-6-(α -methoxycarbonylethyl)-9-methyldecalin (XVI).—A mixture of the keto-ester (XV) (8 g.), toluene (50 c.c.), water (70 c.c.), HCl (conc., 100 c.c.), and acetic acid (10 c.c.) was refluxed for 48 hours with amalgamated zinc (42 g.). Fresh portions of HCl (10 c.c.) were added at intervals of 6 hours. The toluene layer, which was yellow in the beginning, became colorless. The cooled mixture was extracted with ethyl acetate. The ethyl acetate extract and the toluene layer were mixed together. The acid obtained after removing the solvent mixture were esterified with diazomethane, prepared from 8 g. of nitrosomethyl urea, to furnish 4-methoxycarbonyl-6-(α -methoxycarbonylethyl)-9-methyldecalin (XVI), b.p. $145-50^{\circ}/0.05$ mm, yield 5.53 g. (70%). (Found: C, 68.99; H, 9.22. $C_{17}H_{28}O_4$ requires C, 68.92; H, 9.42%).

4-Hydroxymethyl-6-(α -hydroxymethylethyl)-9-methyldecalin (III).—Lithium aluminium hydride (1.7 g.) was refluxed with anhydrous ether (100 c.c.) for 20 mins. The ester (XVI) (7.5 g.) in anhydrous ether (200 c.c.) was then slowly added through the separatory funnel at such a rate as to maintain the reaction mixture at reflux. A gelatinous precipitate appeared immediately. After keeping for 1 hour, the reaction mixture was refluxed for one hour more and left overnight. The product was then decomposed with H_2SO_4 (dil.). To remove any unreduced ester, the product was refluxed for 10 hours with potassium hydroxide (3 g.) in water (3 c.c.) and methanol (25 c.c.). After removing the methanol the product was diluted with water and extracted with ether. The ether was removed and the residue distilled, b.p. $150-52^\circ/9.3 \times 10^{-2}$ mm, yield 4.4 g. (90%), (based on recovered acid). (Found: C, 74.96; H, 11.4. $C_{19}H_{28}O_2$ requires C, 75.01; H, 11.67%). Acidification of the alkaline solution furnished 1.3 g. of the unchanged acid.

4-Acetoxyethyl-6-(α -acetoxyethylethyl)-9-methyldecalin (IV).—A mixture of 4-hydroxymethyl-6-(α -hydroxymethylethyl)-9-methyldecalin (III) (4.8 g.), acetic anhydride (7 c.c.), and pyridine (1 c.c.) was refluxed for 3 hours. The excess of acetic anhydride was removed under diminished pressure. The reaction mixture was then taken in benzene and washed with water. After removing the solvent the product was distilled, b.p. $145-50^\circ/3.5 \times 10^{-2}$ mm, yield 5.6 g. (85%). (Found: C, 70.28; H, 9.77. $C_{20}H_{32}O_4$ requires C, 70.37; H, 9.87%).

Selinene Isomers.—The aforementioned diacetate (IV) (4.4 g.) was dropped in a 25 mm pyrex column, externally heated to $500-575^\circ$ by an electric furnace and packed to a depth of 10 mm with pyrex helices. The addition was conducted in an inert atmosphere by introducing a slow stream of nitrogen at the top of the column. The pyrolysate was collected in a test tube, cooled in a freezing mixture (ice and salt). The pyrolysis product was taken up in ether and washed with water to free it from acetic acid. After removing the ether, the product was distilled, b.p. $113-15^\circ/3$ mm, n_D^{22} 1.5379; λ_{max}^{EtOH} 224 $m\mu$, $\log \epsilon$ 4.2; yield 0.8 g. (29%). (Found: C, 88.17; H, 11.81. $C_{15}H_{24}$ requires C, 88.25; H, 11.77%).